

Contents lists available at ScienceDirect

International Journal of Electrical Power and Energy Systems

journal homepage: www.elsevier.com/locate/ijepes

Cost-Effective Operation of Microgrids: A MILP-Based Energy Management System for Active and Reactive Power Control

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Distributed Energy Resources
Energy Management Systems
Microgrids

ABSTRACT

Microgrids (MGs) have emerged as a potential solution for the integration of Distributed Energy Resources (DERs) into the distribution network. In this sense, to effectively manage MGs, it is essential to implement Energy Management Systems (EMSs). This entails not only performing the unit commitment but also considering the voltage and reactive power technical constraints and managing ancillary services. This paper contributes with a comprehensive EMS for the optimal management of active and reactive power of a generic grid-tied MG composed of Renewable Energy Sources (RESs), Battery Energy Storage Systems (BESSs), Diesel Generator (DGs) units and loads, with the goal of reducing the operating costs of the facility. The EMS includes models for the power electronics units to apply reactive power management and a generic formulation for the management of the startup and shutdown cycles of dispatchable units. Furthermore, a detailed modeling of BESS and DG units is presented, reflecting the actual behavior of the devices. The MG is modeled as a multi-busbar network, with the application of the power flow equations to establish the link between power flows and nodal voltages. All the constraints are linearized to formulate the EMS as a Mixed-Integer Linear Programming (MILP) optimization problem. The EMS is validated in a real facility: the CATEPS Microgrid Living-Lab. The results demonstrate the operational effectiveness of the EMS in different seasons, exhibiting a reduction in costs ranging from 21.84 % in summer to a 5.69 % in winter compared to a scenario with RES production but without energy management. In addition, a comprehensive examination of reactive power and voltage management is presented. Furthermore, an empirical assessment of the power flow equations linearization demonstrated minimal discrepancy in the results when compared with those obtained with the non-linear equations, exhibiting a mean absolute error of 8.8e-5 p.u. and 3.2e-5 rad in voltage magnitude and phase angle, respectively, in the most unfavorable scenario. A sensitivity analysis of the startup and shutdown cycles management of the BESS reveals a negligible effect on operational costs, yet it provides a mechanism for managing the battery stress by reducing the number of startups in a complete week from 28 to 16 in summer and from 37 to 24 in winter. The dependence between the maximum charging and discharging power on the state of charge of the BESS is also assessed in the use case.

1. Introduction

In recent years, the European Union has assumed a commitment to the energy transition. In 2021, the Fit for 55 package was enacted by the European institutions, within the framework of the European Green Deal [1]. The package promoted some challenging goals for the member states for the 2030 year, in terms of reduction of greenhouse gas emissions, penetration of Renewable Energy Sources (RESs) within the generation portfolio [2] and promotion of energy deriving from RES

and energy efficiency in buildings, which represent one of the most energy-consuming sectors at European level [3].

Following these legislative constraints, member states are promoting incentives to foster the installation of a larger share of RESs within national generation portfolios, in replacement of synchronous generators typically installed in traditional coal or gas-fired power stations. RES power plants, mainly represented by Photovoltaic (PV) and Wind Turbine (WT) installations, cannot provide the same performance as synchronous generators in terms of frequency and voltage support [4],

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijepes.2025.110458>

Received 24 July 2024; Received in revised form 25 September 2024; Accepted 3 January 2025

Available online 10 January 2025

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being connected to the distribution network through inverters. Dedicated controllers must be installed on inverters to make them participate in frequency and voltage support [5]. Moreover, PV and WT units are affected by the inherent unpredictability of the primary source, therefore being affected by possible unexpected over- or under-productions. For this reason, these power plants are usually coupled to storage systems, either hydroelectric in large-scale applications [6] or Battery Energy Storage Systems (BESSs) in small scale applications [7]. BESSs are able to absorb possible surplus RES production during peak periods, delivering it back to the network during low RES production periods [8]. Integrated RES-BESS systems can participate in frequency containment and restoration reserves [9]. In addition, BESSs mitigate voltage fluctuations that may derive from fast variations of RES power output [10].

At small scale, RESs and BESSs can be identified as Distributed Energy Resources (DERs): for example, in the residential sector, these devices are installed in the nearby of buildings or on rooftops. Many DERs are connected to each other, along with loads, Electric Vehicles (EVs) charging stations and possible dispatchable generators, such as micro-gas turbines or Diesel Generators (DGs), in the so-called Microgrids (MGs) [11]. MGs may also be made up of plants capable of providing thermal and cooling energy, like boilers, Combined Heat and Power (CHP) units and Combined Cooling, Heat and Power (CCHP) units [12,13]. MGs are usually operated under economic or environmental objectives, aiming to minimize operational costs and/or CO₂ emissions. Moreover, they provide greater flexibility to the distribution network, if compared to the traditional paradigm [14]. Several different applications of the MG concept can be found: remote MGs (for far-away areas and small islands), mobile MGs (transportable on trailer), MGs for military compounds, health care facilities, and university campuses, MGs for data centers, MGs for ports and airports, etc. It is also important to consider how many MG installations can now take place in urban areas, in all those new neighborhoods that are being created as consequence of redevelopment projects on old industrial sites. In these new sustainable urban districts, local green energy production can help reduce the carbon footprint of cities and improve the quality of life, as assessed in [15] where the authors describe the implementation of a MG to feed a Positive Energy District (PED). In the creation of these new sustainable areas, the placement of distributed generation must be carefully evaluated to minimize the impact on the distribution network [16], even considering extreme weather events [17].

The optimal dispatching of the units composing a MG is defined by an Energy Management System (EMS), which is typically the upper level of a Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition System (SCADA). EMSs are in charge, for example, of defining the optimal scheduling of dispatchable units and the optimal active and reactive power provision by DERs: to do this, capability curves of inverters must be embedded within the EMS, as shown in [18], where they are modelled in accordance with Italian technical standards. Moreover, EMSs define the optimal profile of power exchange with the local distribution network, if the MG works in grid-connected mode; if needed, EMSs allow the MG to operate in islanded mode, when required by the distribution system operator. Furthermore, EMSs are used to optimally schedule the operation of BESSs and to apply EV smart charging strategies. The complexity of EMSs is mainly due to the multiple input data that need to be provided to optimally run it. This means economic parameters (electricity purchase and selling prices, maintenance costs, RES curtailment costs, etc.), technical data (performance curves describing the operation of DG plants at partial load, lower and upper bounds for power production, maximum and minimum charging and discharging power for BESSs usually dependent on state of charge, etc.) and environmental parameters (emission factors, etc.) [15]. Moreover, EMSs are usually coupled with forecasting tools used to estimate both loads (electrical, thermal and cooling) and renewable energy production. For instance, in [19] a machine learning probabilistic forecasting approach with robust optimization is proposed to define optimal dispatching for MGs having a high penetration of RESs, while in [20] the analysis focuses on models

used to estimate the loads in a MG. A separate issue concerns the management of electric mobility within a MG, as highlighted in [21], where a study for a remote island fed by a MG with several EV charging points is reported, and in [22], where a method to improve the forecasting accuracy of EV charging demand is proposed. It is very difficult to estimate transport demand, and so the EV charging needs, as it depends not only on environmental and technical factors, but also on behavioral aspects of mobility users.

1.1. Literature review

Several examples of EMSs for MGs can be found in the literature. A comprehensive review of them is presented in [23], and also in [24] where an analysis of the different optimization techniques used to address the energy management problems in MGs is proposed. A comparison of several energy management strategies in MGs is also reported in [25], by highlighting the criticalities in managing intermittent RESs and the importance of applying demand response.

A large portion of the studies present in the literature models the MG as a single busbar system and neglect the impact of reactive power. The application of single busbar model implies that all the power flows among buses and all the relevant voltage phenomena are neglected. Among the studies present in the literature, [26] proposes an EMS to optimally operate a MG located in Egypt with WT, PV and DG units, with the aim of minimizing costs and emissions. In [27] and [28] the authors present a day-ahead EMS for the optimal management of a public postal facility, equipped with micro WTs and a PV system, owning a fleet of EVs for the delivery of freight. Even though these papers introduce an approximation to model the capability curves of inverters to consider reactive power, the proposed model has the potential to result in inverter overload situations, as evidenced by the results. The authors of [29] propose an optimal management strategy for a multi-energy MG operating in energy markets. The proposed scheme is hierarchical, with a lower layer made of single multi-energy MGs and with an upper layer that coordinates the MGs, applying a dynamic price mechanism, and that is interfaced with the distribution network. Nevertheless, a single busbar model is employed to describe the topology of the MGs and reactive power is neglected. A methodology to optimally operate a BESS, providing flexibility to manage PV and WT variability, is provided in [30], for a facility equipped with a microturbine and a DG, too. The purpose of the study is to try to employ the BESS as the unique flexible source, not relying on the DG. However, as in the previous studies, the MG is modelled as a single busbar system and reactive power is neglected.

Other studies apply a multi-busbar model to MGs, to adhere to reality in a better way. For example, in [31] an EMS for a MG feeding residential, commercial and industrial users with PV, WT and BESS units is presented, considering the power flows among buses but neglecting the analysis of voltage phenomena, reactive power exchanges and not trying to limit the number of charging and discharging cycles of the BESS, that could reduce its useful life. The authors of [32] also consider a multi-busbar model to present an EMS for wind farms combined with BESS and distributed generators. The study considers a limitation on the startup and shutdown cycles. However, this last work neglects the impact of reactive power and just consider the management of active power. A two-layer coordinated EMS to optimally manage distribution networks with grid-connected MGs is proposed in [33]. The first layer optimizes the MG operation while the second optimizes the distribution network operation. A multi-busbar model is used to model the MG. However, the management of BESS does not consider the relationship between the SoC and the exchanged power, so possible discrepancies could appear in real implementations. In addition, like other papers, it does not attempt to limit startups to short periods of time. Another study that presents the integration of a multi-busbar model within the EMS is [34], where the study case is a MG with DERs and RESs. In this last paper, Optimal Power Flow (OPF) constraints are also considered. The

authors propose a multi-objective approach, considering economic, environmental and power quality objectives. However, the problem is non-linear (NLP) and non-convex, requiring *meta*-heuristic optimization algorithms to solve it. In addition, BESSs are not considered within the formulation, not assessing the prominent role that they will play in scenarios with high RES penetration, due to their flexibility. Similarly, in [35] an EMS for the optimal dispatching of multi-microgrids requiring *meta*-heuristic optimization algorithms is presented. The proposal considers PV, WT and BESS and models the microgrid as a multi-busbar network. However, the authors just consider active power management, neglecting the effect of reactive power. In [36] the authors propose an EMS to manage virtual power plants connected to a distribution network. The problem considers RES and EV units' management of active and reactive power management through the complete OPF equations. However, the problem is non-linear and non-convex, requiring high computational times and specific solvers. A similar approach is presented in [37] but also considering hydrogen storage as a potential solution to increase reliability and flexibility of the network.

In [38] a mixed-integer second-order cone programming (MISOCP) EMS for MGs incorporating RES, BESS and DG units is proposed. The formulation employs robust optimization to ascertain the viability of the proposed solutions. The EMS manages both active and reactive power, employing a multi-busbar model with a convex formulation of the OPF equations. In [39], some of the same co-authors who contributed to the previous paper presented a MINLP based EMS for islanded MGs that was later linearized as a MILP problem. This proposal includes a multi-busbar model, linearizing the OPF equations through the assumption of knowing estimated values for voltages and active and reactive power flows through lines. The proposed approach entails a hierarchical solution in which the MILP problem is initially solved and subsequently the MINLP. While proposals [38,39] are comprehensive, they lack any stipulations preventing dispatchable units (BESS and DG) from multiple activations and deactivations in short periods of time, not trying to limit the number of startup and shutdown cycles of them, that could reduce its useful life. Additionally, the BESS model does not account for the relationship between maximum power in charging/discharging states and the SoC, which could lead to inaccurate solutions regarding the BESS performance.

To conclude this subsection and with the aim of provide a summary of the literature review, Table 1 outlines the principal attributes of each of the papers studied in this subsection.

1.2. Contributions

As a conclusion of the literature review, few papers propose a comprehensive approach to EMSs for MGs (see Table 1): some of them apply a single busbar model to the MG, preventing the application of power flow equations and the assessment of reactive power exchange by RES inverters and of the impact of RES production fluctuations on nodal voltages. Other papers on the one hand apply a multi-busbar model to the MG, including the OPF equations, but on the other hand do not provide a detailed insight into the role that BESSs and dispatchable DERs play in MGs management, some of them without even considering reactive power control. It has been shown that the influence of startup and shutdown cycles of dispatchable units (such as BESS or DGs) is often overlooked. Furthermore, the relationship between SoC and the power that BESS can deliver is frequently disregarded, which can result in inaccurate assessments of BESS performance. Many proposals employ non-convex and non-linear formulations, requiring heuristic-based solvers to obtain the solution of the problem. Others utilize convex quadratic programming techniques, while another group employs hierarchical approaches. Furthermore, it has been observed that the use-cases presented in the literature are typically constructed using synthetic MGs. In addition, some of the papers lack comprehensive information regarding the characteristics of the network or the assets.

Given the state of the art, the aim of the present paper is to define a comprehensive EMS for the optimal operation of a grid-tied MG composed of distributed RES units (PVs and WTs), distributed dispatchable units (BESS and DGs) and loads, with the goal of reducing the operating costs of the facility, and considering the limitations previously identified in the state-of-the-art. The EMS has been modelled as a Mixed-Integer Linear Programming (MILP) problem, to ensure the existence of an optimal solution and that it represents the global minimum. In addition, linear formulations are often preferred over convex quadratic formulations due to their simplicity and the extensive support and maturity of the solvers that are available. This approach also reduces the computational capacity required. Within the EMS, dedicated models for power electronics units are inserted, taking into account the capability curves of converters. This allows to consider the impact of reactive power on the nodal voltage amplitudes, as well as managing potential penalties for reactive power exchange with the external grid. Power flow equations are linearized and also included in the EMS to link power flows and nodal voltages. Moreover, a detailed model for BESS is

Table 1

Summary of the literature review. An empty cell indicate that the paper does not address the characteristic. The symbol ▲ denotes that the paper discusses the use of BESS but does not consider the relation between exchanged power and SoC. The symbol ◆ denotes that the paper is using EVs as energy storage. The symbol ■ denotes that the paper addresses the use of DGs but does not consider the inherent constraints of such systems.

Paper	Optimization model	Reactive power control	OPF equations	Implementation of inverters' capability curves	Limits ON/OFF cycles of dispatchable units	Use case	DERs			
							PV	WT	BESS	DG
[27,28]	MILP	✓		✓		Synthetic	✓	✓	◆	
[29]	Hierarchical MILP					Synthetic	✓	✓	▲	■
[30]	Quadratic Programming					Synthetic	✓	✓	▲	■
[31]	MILP		Just active power.			Synthetic	✓	✓	▲	
[32]	MILP		DC power flow		✓	Synthetic		✓	▲	✓
[33]	Hierarchical MILP	✓	Brach equations linearized	✓		Synthetic	✓	✓	▲	■
[34]	Non-convex NLP	✓	Non-convex equations			Synthetic	✓	✓		
[35]	Non-convex NLP		Non-convex equation just for active power			Synthetic	✓	✓	▲	
[36,37]	Non-convex NLP	✓	Non-convex equations	✓		Synthetic	✓	✓	◆	
[38]	MISOCP	✓	SOCP formulation	✓		Synthetic	✓	✓	▲	✓
[39]	Hierarchical MILP-MINLP	✓	Linear formulation needing estimated grid values.	✓		Synthetic		✓	▲	✓
This paper	MILP	✓	Nodal equations linearized	✓	✓	Real facility	✓	✓	✓	✓

provided, taking into account the dependence of the maximum charging and discharging power on the State of Charge (SoC) and considering constraints on the number of charging, discharging and shutdown cycles, needed to extend the useful life of the battery. Regarding DG generators, ramp-up and ramp-down constraints have been included in the EMS formulation, along with maximum and minimum operating regimes, to mimic the real behaviour of the device. A graphical representation of the EMS operation is depicted in Fig. 1.

In order to strengthen the proposed EMS, its validation is carried out in the Microgrid Living-Lab installed at the CATEPS building of the Higher Polytechnic School of the University of Seville, equipped with all the aforementioned technologies. The technical characteristics of the facility (MG network and the assets deployed) are extensively commented, with the objective of facilitate their use by other researchers. Results are here presented and deeply commented, showing the operations of the MG in different seasons. Additionally, a detailed focus is provided on reactive power and voltage management. An empirical validation of the power flow equations linearization is also conducted, comparing the results obtained under both the linearized and non-linearized formulations. Finally, the effect of the minimum number of ON/OFF charging and discharging cycles and the dependence of power with the SoC in the BESS model is also evaluated.

The main contributions of the present paper are represented by:

- Inclusion of dedicated models for power electronics, which consider capability curves and power factor limitations, allowing the assessment of reactive power management.
- Comprehensive approach to manage dispatchable units, whereby minimum ON/OFF periods are considered in order to avoid the occurrence of multiple startups and shutdowns in short periods of time.
- Application of multi-busbar model of the MG, together linearized power flow equations. Validation of the equations through comparison of the results with the complete non-linear power flow equations.
- Detailed modelling of BESS, considering technical characteristics as the relation between maximum power in charging/discharging

phases and SoC. Including a sensitivity analysis on the limitation on the startup/shutdown cycles limitation.

- Comprehensive approach to manage DG units, taking into account the technical constraints inherent to such systems, considering its operating conditions, including ramp-up/ramp-down rates, minimum operating regime, and the number of ON/OFF cycles.
- Application of the EMS to a real test-case, considering the characteristics of actual facilities and avoiding the use of synthetic use-cases.

The paper is organized as follows: Section 2 details the mathematical formulation of the EMS, Section 3 describes the CATEPS Microgrid Living-Lab, employed as test case, Section 4 presents and discusses the results, while Section 5 is dedicated to conclusions and also provides some possible further developments of the study.

2. EMS mathematical formulation

In this section, the mathematical model of the EMS is described. The model is built as a MILP optimization problem, taking advantage of its simplicity and the extensive support and maturity of the solvers that are available compared with other kinds of convex formulations. The objective of the EMS is to minimize the operational cost of the MG while considering the technical constraints of it, maintaining the MG between feasible operational limits. The inputs of the model are the forecasted power production of all the RES units, the SoC of the BESS at the beginning of the optimization cycle, the forecasted consumption of MG, the technical performance parameters of all the energy sources of the MG (power ratings, ramp-up/down profiles, network admittance matrix, etc.) and, of course, the parameters related to costs. The outputs of the model are the power profiles (both active and reactive) of all dispatchable units and the voltage phasors and powers at all the nodes of the MG. Unless otherwise specified, all electrical units presented in this paper are expressed in the per-unit (p.u.) system, with S_B and V_B representing the base power and base voltage, respectively. A positive value in a power variable indicates the injection of power into the node, while a negative power value indicates the absorption of power. The formulation is presented in a generic form and can be applied to any MG. The

Fig. 1. Graphical representation of the EMS operation.

time horizon is represented by T , with time being discretized into N time steps. The time interval between steps is denoted by Δt ($\Delta t = T/N$). In general, variables have two superscripts: the first indicates the asset to which it refers (e.g., PV, BESS, DG, etc.) while the second describes some characteristic of the variable. In the case of a general formulation applicable to multiple assets, the superscript symbol X is employed. Subscripts serve to indicate the index of the generating unit and the time index.

2.1. Power electronics unit model

In this subsection, the constraints related to the assets connected to the MG by means of power electronics units (e.g. inverters, rectifiers, and power converters) are presented.

First, these assets must meet the power rating technical limits of the power electronics (1) :

$$(S_{i,t}^{X,max})^2 \geq (P_{i,t}^X)^2 + (Q_{i,t}^X)^2 \quad (1)$$

where $P_{i,t}^X$ and $Q_{i,t}^X$ are the active and reactive powers of the i th asset of technology X at time t and $S_{i,t}^{X,max}$ the maximum apparent power that can be delivered by the power electronics. Inequality (1) is a quadratic expression, but it can be linearized considering that the constraint just defines that the hypotenuse (conformed by a right triangle whose catheti are P and Q) must be equal or lower than the apparent power of the inverter. This is the same as considering that the apparent power delivered by the inverter must be within a circle of radius the maximum rating of it. Therefore, constraint (1) can be linearized by considering a set of N^{PW} linear constraints with the form of (2). As N^{PW} increases, the set of constraints (2) becomes closer to the non-linear capability curve (1). Thus, the higher N^{PW} parameter the better.

$$S_i^{X,max} \geq P_{i,t}^X \cos(2\pi n/N^{PW}) + Q_{i,t}^X \sin(2\pi n/N^{PW}), \forall n \in [1, N^{PW}] \quad (2)$$

Second, power electronics units can operate only within certain power factor limits. Considering that active power could be positive or negative, as could be the case of units that include a rectifier (e.g., the rectifier of a BESS), constraint (3) must hold to maintain the power factor between feasible limits in the four-quadrants:

$$-\tan(\phi_i^{X,PF}) |P_{i,t}^X| \leq Q_{i,t}^X \leq \tan(\phi_i^{X,PF}) |P_{i,t}^X| \quad (3)$$

where $\phi_i^{X,PF}$ is obtained as $\phi_i^{X,PF} = \arccos(PF_i^X)$, being PF_i^X the minimum power factor at which the unit can operate. Of course, the absolute value function is non-linear. Appendix A. shows the MILP implementation of this function. If the unit can only inject energy into the grid, as is the case of PV units, the absolute value function it is not needed in constraint (3).

Lastly, it is necessary to consider that some units could deliver a maximum active power value ($P_{i,t}^{X,max}$) lower than the nominal apparent power. Thus, it is necessary to impose (4) to consider this possibility. If the unit cannot absorb power (e.g., a PV inverter), the value on the left-hand side of (4) will be substituted by zero.

$$-P_i^{X,max} \leq P_{i,t}^X \leq P_i^{X,max} \quad (4)$$

In contrast to other models used in the literature, the model presented in this subsection ensures that the power electronics operates only within its capability curve, thereby preventing both out-of-range operating zones and overload conditions.

2.2. Dispatchable units ON/OFF limitations

In this subsection, a set of constraints to establish minimum ON/OFF periods for dispatchable units (e.g., BESS or DGs) are presented. This set of constraints can be applied to all kinds of dispatchable units available in MGs. However, they only cover the case of dispatchable units with

$P_{i,t}^X \geq 0$ (i.e., they are not bidirectional). Adaptation in the case of bidirectional dispatchable units such as BESS is discussed in its own subsection.

In this sense, to avoid that dispatchable units are turned ON/OFF multiple times in short periods of time, constraint (5) is introduced to maintain the i th unit of technology X ON for at least $N^{X,on}$ timesteps:

$$a_{i,t}^{X,tron} \leq (1/N^{X,on}) \sum_{k=t}^{t+N^{X,on}-1} a_{i,k}^{X,on} \quad (5)$$

where $a_{i,t}^{X,on}$ is a binary variable indicating that the unit is ON at time step t and $a_{i,t}^{X,tron}$ is a binary variable indicating that the unit has been turned ON at time step t . The value of $N^{X,on}$ is obtained as $N^{X,on} = \lceil T^{X,on}/\Delta t \rceil$, where $\lceil x \rceil$ denotes the ceiling function of x and $T^{X,on}$ is the minimum time that the unit must be ON.

Similarly, if one wants to impose that the unit must be maintained OFF for a certain time after it has been turned OFF, constraint (6) could also be included in the model of the dispatchable unit. In this case, $a_{i,t}^{X,toff}$ is a binary variable denoting that the i th unit has been turned OFF at time t and $N^{X,off}$ represents the number of time steps that the unit must remain OFF.

$$a_{i,t}^{X,toff} \leq 1 - (1/N^{X,off}) \sum_{k=t}^{t+N^{X,off}-1} a_{i,k}^{X,on} \quad (6)$$

To obtain the binary variable $a_{i,t}^{X,on}$ indicating whether the unit is ON or OFF, classical big-M constraints in (7) and (8) are imposed:

$$P_{i,t}^X \geq \epsilon - M(1 - a_{i,t}^{X,on}) \quad (7)$$

$$P_{i,t}^X \leq M a_{i,t}^{X,on} \quad (8)$$

where M is a big positive number and ϵ a small positive tolerance to simulate a $>$ inequality.

In addition, constraints (9) and (10) are included in the unit model to obtain the binary variables that indicate when the unit has been turned ON or OFF:

$$a_{i,t}^{X,tron} - a_{i,t}^{X,toff} = a_{i,t}^{X,on} - a_{i,t-1}^{X,on} \quad (9)$$

$$a_{i,t}^{X,tron} + a_{i,t}^{X,toff} \leq 1 \quad (10)$$

2.3. Renewable energy source units

The active power generation profiles of the RES units (e.g., PVs or WTs) are inputs for the model (obtained through forecasting techniques). However, in the case of reactive power, RES units can adapt the injection/absorption to the grid by means of the power inverters. Thus $Q_{i,t}^X$ of RES units is a decision variable. Of course, this is possible if the inverter rating constraints are met. Therefore, it is possible to use the RES inverter as a reactive energy dispatchable unit including a set of constraints as (2) and (3) in the model.

2.4. Battery energy storage system

In this subsection, the model for the BESS units is introduced. First, since the BESS is connected by means of an inverter/rectifier to the electric network, a set of constraints (2) to (4) are included. In addition, as a dispatchable asset, a set of constraints described in subsection 2.2 must be included to control the ON/OFF cycles of the unit. However, as stated before, these constraints only consider the case of dispatchable units that only inject active power into the grid (e.g., DGs or CHPs). Thus, if the unit is a battery that can discharge (inject) or charge (absorb), these constraints only cover the discharging case. Therefore, it is necessary to add another set of constraints (5)-(6) and (9)-(10) to model the charging case. The superscript *on* in the binary variables must be replaced by *ch* and *dis* in each of the two sets of constraints to

distinguish the charging and discharging variables. Moreover, different number of minimum charging ($N^{BESS,on, ch}$, $N^{BESS,off, ch}$) and discharging cycles ($N^{BESS,on, dis}$, $N^{BESS,off, dis}$) could be defined. In addition to these, constraints (11) and (12) must be included to obtain the $a_{i,t}^{BESS, ch}$ binary variable, which indicates whether the unit is in a charging state. Of course, constraint (13) must hold between ch and dis variables. If both variables are zero, the unit is OFF. Thus, the binary variable $a_{i,t}^{BESS, on}$ that indicates if the unit is ON or OFF is obtained with the equality (14).

$$-P_{i,t}^{BESS} \geq \epsilon - M(1 - a_{i,t}^{BESS, ch}) \quad (11)$$

$$-P_{i,t}^{BESS} \leq M a_{i,t}^{BESS, ch} \quad (12)$$

$$a_{i,t}^{BESS, dis} + a_{i,t}^{BESS, ch} \leq 1 \quad (13)$$

$$a_{i,t}^{BESS, dis} + a_{i,t}^{BESS, ch} = a_{i,t}^{BESS, on} \quad (14)$$

The energy model of the BESS is presented in (15):

$$W_{i,t+1}^{BESS} = W_{i,t}^{BESS} - \Delta t \left(P_{i,t}^{BESS} \left(a_{i,t}^{BESS, ch} \eta_i^{ch} + a_{i,t}^{BESS, dis} (1/\eta_i^{dis}) \right) + W_{i,t}^{BESS} \tau_i^{BESS, sd} \right) \quad (15)$$

where $W_{i,t}^{BESS}$ is the energy stored by the i th unit at time t , η_i^{ch} and η_i^{dis} are the efficiency while charging and discharging, respectively; and $\tau_i^{BESS, sd}$ is the self-discharge loss expressed as the per unit loss of stored energy per hour.

As can be noticed, (15) is a non-linear function due to the product of continuous variable $P_{i,t}^{BESS}$ with binary variables $a_{i,t}^{BESS, ch}$ and $a_{i,t}^{BESS, dis}$ to model the selection of charging/discharging efficiencies. These non-linear terms can be linearized by substituting them by two auxiliary continuous variables $g_{i,t}^{BESS, dis} \triangleq a_{i,t}^{BESS, dis} P_{i,t}^{BESS}$ and $g_{i,t}^{BESS, ch} \triangleq a_{i,t}^{BESS, ch} P_{i,t}^{BESS}$, obtained as described in Appendix B. With this substitution, (16) is the linear equivalent of (15).

$$W_{i,t+1}^{BESS} = W_{i,t}^{BESS} - \Delta t \left(g_{i,t}^{BESS, ch} \eta_i^{ch} + g_{i,t}^{BESS, dis} (1/\eta_i^{dis}) + W_{i,t}^{BESS} \tau_i^{BESS, sd} \right) \quad (16)$$

Constraints (17) and (18) are included to limit the maximum and minimum state of charge the battery can reach:

$$W_{i,t}^{BESS} \leq W_i^{BESS, cap} SoC_i^{BESS, max} \quad (17)$$

$$W_{i,t}^{BESS} \geq W_i^{BESS, cap} SoC_i^{BESS, min} \quad (18)$$

where $SoC_i^{BESS, max}$ and $SoC_i^{BESS, min}$ are the maximum and minimum SoC the battery can reach and $W_i^{BESS, cap}$ is the rated capacity of the battery.

The minimum power at which the BESS must operate, both in charging and discharging mode, can be defined with constraints (19) and (20). Of course, if wanted, different minimum values could be established for the charging and discharging cases.

$$P_{i,t}^{BESS} \geq -P_i^{BESS, min} a_{i,t}^{BESS, ch} \quad (19)$$

$$P_{i,t}^{BESS} \leq P_i^{BESS, min} a_{i,t}^{BESS, dis} \quad (20)$$

In addition, the relationship between the SoC and the maximum power at which the battery can be charged/discharged must be considered. Typically, when charging from a low SoC, the maximum rated power can be delivered to the battery. However, when a certain SoC is reached while charging, the maximum power accepted by the BESS starts to decrease until it reaches its full capacity. Similarly, when discharging from a high SoC, the maximum rated power can be extracted from the battery. However, when a certain SoC is reached while discharging, the maximum power that can be extracted from the BESS starts to decrease until it reaches its minimum capacity.

This behavior can be modeled by defining two additional linear

constraints linking the SoC with the power exchanged by the BESS. Specifically, inequality (21) models the charging scenario while (22) models the discharging one. In these constraints, $m_i^{BESS, ch}$ and $m_i^{BESS, dis}$ are two constants obtained from equations (23) and (24), where L_i^{ch} and L_i^{dis} are the SoC limits at which injected/absorbed power starts to decrease. This formulation differs from others in the literature in that it avoids the use of piecewise functions, which considers conditional formulation, introducing multiple binary variables. In this sense, this formulation just introduces two linear inequalities into the problem, reducing computational effort.

$$P_{i,t}^{BESS} \geq m_i^{BESS, ch} (SoC_{i,t}^{BESS} - 1) \quad (21)$$

$$P_{i,t}^{BESS} \leq m_i^{BESS, dis} SoC_{i,t}^{BESS} \quad (22)$$

$$m_i^{BESS, ch} = P_i^{BESS, max} / (1 - L_i^{ch}) \quad (23)$$

$$m_i^{BESS, dis} = P_i^{BESS, max} / L_i^{dis} \quad (24)$$

As a summary of the BESS operation, Fig. 2 shows graphically the feasible operational range defined by the constraints presented in this subsection.

2.5. Diesel generators

As a dispatchable unit, the model of the DG must complain with the restrictions imposed in subsection 2.2 to limit the ON/OFF cycles. Thus, a set of constraints like the ones from (5) to (10) are included for each DG unit.

In addition to the minimum ON/OFF time limitations, due to the nature of DGs, constraints (25) and (26) are included to limit the ramp-up ($P_i^{DG, RU}$) and ramp-down ($P_i^{DG, RD}$) rates respectively. The two aforementioned parameters are given in W/h in the datasheets (subsequently transformed into the per-unit system as all the variables in the EMS formulation).

$$P_{i,t}^{DG} - P_{i,t-1}^{DG} \leq \Delta t P_i^{DG, RU} \quad (25)$$

$$P_{i,t-1}^{DG} - P_{i,t}^{DG} \leq \Delta t P_i^{DG, RD} \quad (26)$$

Moreover, DGs usually have a minimum power operating regime. To reach this operating regime, they need a certain period of time in the startup. In a similar way, they may need a certain time to shut down. Thus, to consider this possibility, constraint (27) is used to establish a minimum power in the stationary operating regime.

$$\left(a_{i,t}^{DG} - \sum_{k=t-N^{DG, tr_{on}}-1}^t a_{i,k}^{DG, tr_{on}} - \sum_{k=t}^{t+N^{DG, tr_{off}}-1} a_{i,k}^{DG, tr_{off}} \right) P_i^{DG, min} \leq P_{i,t}^{DG} \leq P_i^{DG, max} \quad (27)$$

The left-hand side of the inequality establishes a minimum power injection in the stationary regime. The minimum power injection is deactivated when the unit is OFF or when the unit is in the startup/shutdown periods. Specifically, the minimum power injection is deactivated for $N^{DG, tr_{on}}$ and $N^{DG, tr_{off}}$ timesteps for the startup and shutdown respectively. These variables are obtained as (28) and (29) respectively:

$$N^{DG, tr_{on}} = \lceil P_i^{DG, min} / (\Delta t P_i^{DG, RU}) \rceil \quad (28)$$

$$N^{DG, tr_{off}} = \lceil P_i^{DG, min} / (\Delta t P_i^{DG, RD}) \rceil \quad (29)$$

where $\lceil x \rceil$ denotes the ceiling function of x . It is worth mentioning that (27) implicitly imposes that $N^{DG, on} \geq N^{DG, tr_{on}} + N^{DG, tr_{off}}$ must be satisfied for the unit to operate. Fig. 3 shows graphically the interpretation of the variables described in this subsection.

Fig. 2. Feasible operational regions of the BESS.

Fig. 3. DG startup and shutdown variables.

Finally, the production cost of the i th DG unit at time t ($C_{i,t}^{DG}$) is presented in (30):

$$C_{i,t}^{DG} = c^{fuel} S_B \Delta t \left(a_{i,t}^{DG} \rho_i P_i^{DG,n} + \sigma_i P_{i,t}^{DG} \right) \quad (30)$$

where c^{fuel} is the fuel cost (in €/L), ρ_i and σ_i are the fuel intercept and the fuel slope obtained from the datasheet of the DG (both units in L/kWh) [40,41], $P_i^{DG,n}$ is the nominal power of the unit and S_B is the base power used in the per-unit operations.

2.6. Electric network model

The simplest way to model the electric network of a MG is to use a single bus representation, in which all assets are connected to the same electrical point. As evidenced in the introduction, this is the most common approach observed in the literature. Despite the simplicity of this modeling approach, which merely introduces two constraints to ensure the balance of active and reactive powers, it fails to consider the link between power flows (active and reactive) and nodal voltages. Additionally, it disregards the technical constraints associated with electrical variables, such as voltage limits. To address this limitation, the proposed EMS incorporates the power flow equations into the formulation. However, power flow equations are non-linear. Thus, in this subsection, a linearized version of the power flow equations is presented.

Considering a MG with N_n nodes (or buses), the complex power phasor $\bar{S}_{i,t}$ at node i and time t is given by (31):

$$\bar{S}_{i,t} = \bar{V}_{i,t} \bar{I}_{i,t}^* = \bar{V}_{i,t} \sum_{k=0}^{N_n-1} \bar{Y}_{ik}^* \bar{V}_{k,t}^* \quad (31)$$

where $\bar{V}_{i,t}$ and $\bar{I}_{i,t}$ are the voltage and injected current phasors at node i , while \bar{Y}_{ik} denotes the i, k element of the network admittance matrix. It should be noted that $*$ represent the complex-conjugate. As usual in power flow notation, the power at nodes $i = 0, \dots, (N_n - 1)$ is composed by the sum of the net injected powers of the elements connected to that node. Node 0 is designated as the slack of the network (reference bus), with $\bar{V}_{0,t} = 1 \angle 0$ (p.u.). In this sense, the Point of Common Coupling (PCC) of the MG with the distribution network will be considered the slack node.

As stated, (31) is non-linear. A possible linearization of it is to obtain the first order Taylor expansion centered at operational point $\bar{V} = 1 \angle 0$ p.u.. The result of this linearization is shown in (32).

$$\bar{S}_{i,t} \approx \sum_{k=0}^{N_n-1} \bar{Y}_{ik}^* + \left(\sum_{k=0}^{N_n-1} \bar{Y}_{ik}^* \right) (\bar{V}_{i,t} - 1 \angle 0) + \sum_{k=0}^{N_n-1} (\bar{Y}_{ik}^* (\bar{V}_{k,t} - 1 \angle 0)) \quad (32)$$

In low-voltage networks, shunt admittances are insignificant and can be neglected. Thus, the sum of elements at columns (and rows) in the admittance matrix is zero, simplifying (32) to (33).

$$\bar{S}_{i,t} = \sum_{k=0}^{N_n-1} \bar{Y}_{ik}^* (\bar{V}_{k,t} - 1 \angle 0) \quad (33)$$

Equation (33) can be rewritten in rectangular form as (34) considering that if the per unit system is adopted and operate in radians, $\bar{V}_{i,t} = V_{i,t} \angle \delta_{i,t}$ can be approximated as $\bar{V}_{i,t} \approx V_{i,t} + j \delta_{i,t}$, being $V_{i,t}$ and $\delta_{i,t}$ the voltage magnitude and phase angle at node i and time t . In this context, j is the imaginary unit. This is a valid approximation when voltage magnitude values are not too far from the base value and phase angle differences across lines are not large, as is the case of small size electrical networks as MGs ($\Re e(\bar{V}_{i,t}) = V_{i,t} \cos(\delta_{i,t}) \approx V_{i,t}$ and $\Im m(\bar{V}_{i,t}) = V_{i,t} \sin(\delta_{i,t}) \approx \delta_{i,t}$).

Splitting the real and imaginary parts in (34) and setting $\Delta V_{k,t} = V_{k,t} - 1$, equations (35) and (36) are the linearized power flow equations for the active and reactive powers at node i and time t . Where G_{ik} and B_{ik} are the conductance and susceptance of the branch between nodes i and k , respectively. Consequently, a set of N_n constraints for each time interval in the form of (35) and (36) are included in the model to consider the electrical network of the MG. A validation of the linearization of the power flow equations will be presented in the results section.

$$P_{i,t} + jQ_{i,t} = \sum_{k=0}^{N_n-1} (G_{ik} - jB_{ik})(V_{k,t} - 1) - \sum_{k=0}^{N_n-1} (G_{ik} - jB_{ik})j\delta_{k,t} \quad (34)$$

$$P_{i,t} = \sum_{k=0}^{N_n-1} (G_{ik}\Delta V_{k,t} - B_{ik}\delta_{k,t}) \quad (35)$$

$$Q_{i,t} = - \sum_{k=0}^{N_n-1} (G_{ik}\delta_{k,t} + B_{ik}\Delta V_{k,t}) \quad (36)$$

Introducing the network model into the optimization process allows to include suitable voltage and phase angle bounds to ensure the proper operation of the MG (37)–(38).

$$V_{min} \leq V_{i,t} \leq V_{max} \quad (37)$$

$$\delta_{min} \leq \delta_{i,t} \leq \delta_{max} \quad (38)$$

Finally, the cost of both active and reactive power absorbed/delivered from/to the distribution network (i.e., at node 0) at time t is presented in equation (39):

$$C_t^{grid} = S_B \Delta t \left(P_{0,t} \left(c_t^{P,buy} \left(1 - a_{0,t}^P \right) + c_t^{P,sell} a_{0,t}^P \right) + Q_{0,t} \left(c_t^{Q,buy} \left(1 - a_{0,t}^Q \right) - c_t^{Q,sell} a_{0,t}^Q \right) \right) \quad (39)$$

where $c_t^{P,buy}$ and $c_t^{P,sell}$ are the cost and revenue of active power energy at time t respectively while $c_t^{Q,buy}$ and $c_t^{Q,sell}$ are the penalties for reactive power absorption and injection respectively. The binary variables $a_{0,t}^X$ are employed to indicate whether active power (superscript P) or reactive power (superscript Q) is flowing into ($a_{0,t}^X = 1$) or from ($a_{0,t}^X = 0$) the distribution network. These variables are obtained using constraints as (7) and (8). As always, S_B is the base power used in the per-unit operations.

As can be noticed, (39) is non-linear due to the multiplication of the binary variables $a_{0,t}^X$ with the active and reactive power continuous decision variables to model the selection of buying or selling costs. As happened in the battery model, the product of binary with a continuous variable can be linearized by defining an auxiliary variable obtained as explained in Appendix B. Thus, obtaining two auxiliary variables $g_{0,t}^P \triangleq a_{0,t}^P P_{0,t}$ and $g_{0,t}^Q \triangleq a_{0,t}^Q Q_{0,t}$, equation (39) can be rewritten in a linear form as (40):

$$C_t^{grid} = S_B \Delta t \left(c_t^{P,buy} (P_{0,t} - g_{0,t}^P) + c_t^{P,sell} g_{0,t}^P + c_t^{Q,buy} (Q_{0,t} - g_{0,t}^Q) - c_t^{Q,sell} g_{0,t}^Q \right) \quad (40)$$

2.7. Objective function

The objective of the model is to minimize the operational costs of the MG. In other words, the objective is to find the solution that reduces the total price paid for energy subject to the constraints of the device models described in this section. In this sense, two primary sources of economic expenses are present in the MG model: the cost of the energy exchanged with external grid and the cost of the fuel for the DGs. Thus, the objective function can be described as follows:

$$\min \sum_{t=0}^{N-1} \left(C_t^{grid} + \sum_{i=0}^{N^{DG}-1} C_{i,t}^{DG} \right) \quad (41)$$

where C_t^{grid} and $C_{i,t}^{DG}$ are the cost of the electrical energy exchanged with the distribution network (eq. (40)) and the cost of the fuel for the i th DG (eq. (30)), respectively. N and N^{DG} denote the number of timesteps for the optimization horizon ($N = T/\Delta t$) and the number of DG units in the MG, respectively.

3. Use case: CATEPS Microgrid Living-Lab

The experimental validation of the proposed EMS has been carried

out in the Microgrid Living-Lab deployed at the CATEPS building of the Higher Polytechnic School of the University of Seville. This recently constructed building houses the laboratories, administrative areas and offices of the Polytechnic School.

The CATEPS building is shown in Fig. 4. The building is composed of three distinct sections: an open-plan laboratory area, an administrative zone, and the offices and research laboratories. The open-plan laboratory is located on the west side, whereas the administrative area is located on the east side. Both areas are two independent three-floor sub-buildings, separated by a patio. On top of these two structures, four three-floor sub-buildings are situated transversally, housing offices and research laboratories (see Fig. 4).

The Microgrid Living-Lab is a Smart Grid testbed integrated into the building's three-phase low-voltage network, which is connected to the medium voltage distribution network through its own secondary distribution substation. The microgrid was fully operational at the beginning of 2023. The Microgrid Living-Lab network can be modeled as a radial grid with twelve busbars. Fig. 5 shows the single-line model of the MG. In this circuit model, the total energy consumption of the six previously described areas of the building is represented as six single aggregated loads connected each one to its corresponding node. In this sense, the load at N1 comprises the consumption of the open-plan laboratory, the load at N2 the consumption of the administrative area and the loads at N4 to N7 the consumption of each of the four transversal sub-buildings respectively. The consumption at these nodes comprises a considerable number of individual loads, some of them three-phase and others single phase. The latter are distributed equally in all phases in accordance with Spanish regulations [42]. Consequently, the aggregate load at the aforementioned nodes is predominantly balanced when all these loads are combined.

The assets deployed in the CATEPS Microgrid Living-Lab are depicted in Fig. 6. The list of the elements and the technical specifications of them are provided below:

- A total of four PV fields, each comprising 28 PV panels arranged in two strings. The panels are monocrystalline of Passivated Emitter and Rear Cell (PERC) technology, each one with a rated power of 650Wp. Each PV field has a three-phase inverter with a rated power of 15kVA. The four PV fields are of equal specifications and are installed in the same mounting position and with the same azimuth angle.
- A BESS composed of six 48Vdc Lithium Iron Phosphate (LiFePO4) battery packs connected in parallel. Each battery pack has a nominal capacity of 280Ah. The BESS is equipped with six single-phase inverters/rectifiers, which are connected in two groups of three and synchronized to form a three-phase system. Each inverter/rectifier has a rated power of 10kVA.

Fig. 4. CATEPS building. The Microgrid Living-Lab is deployed in this building.

Fig. 5. CATEPS Microgrid Living-Lab network model.

- Two H-Type Darreus vertical WTs, each with a rated power of 3kWp. Both WTs are managed by the same inverter with a rated power of 5kVA.
- One DG with both on-grid and backup capabilities. The DG is constructed with a four-stroke V16 diesel engine and an 800kVA three-phase generator.
- A control room equipped with a SCADA system for monitoring plant operations and data collection.

3.1. Input parameters and test scenarios

In this subsection, the input parameters for the EMS are described. The EMS operates with a time horizon of $T = 24$ h with $\Delta t = 15$ min timestep, resulting in 96 timesteps per optimization horizon. The active power production of the RESs and the load consumption (both active and reactive) are provided by deterministic machine learning

forecasting techniques [43]. It should be noted that, although a fixed optimization horizon without overlapping has been selected to obtain the results, there is no inherent limitation in the formulation to be implemented in a rolling-horizon approach, thereby reducing possible impacts of stochasticity in renewable energy sources (RES).

As mentioned above, the grid is modeled as a twelve-bus bar network as shown in Fig. 5. The characteristics of each branch are reported in Table 2. The bus bar N0 is considered the slack of the network ($V_0 = 1$ p.u., $\delta_0 = 0$ rad). The voltage and power bases for the per unit operations are 400 V and 30kVA respectively (nominal line voltage of the grid and maximum power of the BESS respectively). The voltage limits (V_{min} , V_{max}) have been set to be between 0.95 and 1.05p.u. while the voltage phase limits (δ_{min} , δ_{max}) have been set to be between -0.1 and 0.1 rad.

PV fields at nodes N8 to N11 have a maximum power rating of $S_i^{PV,max} = 15$ kVA and $P_i^{PV,max} = 15$ kW. The minimum power factor at which PV inverters can operate is $PF_i^{PV} = 0.85$ (both inductive and capacitive). The WT inverter has a maximum power rating of $S_1^{WT,max} = 5$ kVA and $P_1^{WT,max} = 5$ kW. The WT inverter can operate at a minimum power factor of $PF_1^{WT} = 0.8$ (both inductive and capacitive). In both RES units, reactive power $Q_{i,t}^X$ is a decision variable subject to constraints (2)-(3).

The BESS at node N3 has a rated capacity of $W^{BESS,cap} = 80.64$ kWh.

Table 2

Characteristics of each of the branches of the microgrid.

Branch	Cable Type	Length (m)
N0-N1	RZ1-K(AS) 4x(3x150mm)	36
N1-N2	RZ1-K(AS) 4x(3x150mm)	5
N2-N3	RZ1-K(AS) 4x50mm	21
N2-N4	RZ1-K(AS) 4x70mm	34
N2-N5	RZ1-K(AS) 4x(2x95mm)	31
N2-N6	RZ1-K(AS) 4x70mm	57
N2-N7	RZ1-K(AS) 4x150mm	60
N4-N8	RZ1-K(AS) 4x10mm	54
N5-N9	RZ1-K(AS) 4x10mm	77
N6-N10	RZ1-K(AS) 4x6mm	57
N7-N11	RZ1-K(AS) 4x6mm	57

Fig. 6. Assets deployed at the CATEPS Microgrid Living-Lab.

The BESS power electronics have a maximum power rating of $S^{BESS,max} = 30\text{kVA}$ and $P^{BESS,max} = 30\text{ kW}$ both in charging and discharging modes. The minimum active power injection/absorption is $P^{BESS,min} = 5\text{ kW}$. It is not possible for the BESS's power electronics to manage reactive power adjustments. Consequently, the power factor of the BESS is always equal to one $PF_i^{BESS} = 1$. The state of charge operational range ($SoC^{BESS,min}$, $SoC^{BESS,max}$) have been set to be between 0.1p.u. and 0.95p.u. Charging (η_i^{ch}) and discharging (η_i^{dis}) efficiencies are 0.93 and 0.95 respectively. The self-discharging rate is $\tau^{BESS,sd} = 5 \times 10^{-5}$ p.u./h. The BESS must be charging or discharging for at least of 3 timesteps after turn-on charging/discharging ($N^{BESS,on,ch}$ and $N^{BESS,on,dis}$ variables) and at least 1 timestep OFF after turn-off charging/discharging ($N^{BESS,off,ch}$ and $N^{BESS,off,dis}$ variables). The SoC limits at which injected/absorbed power starts to decrease in charging (L_i^{ch}) and discharging (L_i^{dis}) modes are 0.8 p.u. and 0.2 p.u. respectively.

The DG at node N3 has a maximum power rating of $S^{DG,max} = 800\text{kVA}$ and $P^{DG,max} = 640\text{ kW}$. The DG works at a fixed $PF^{DG} = 0.8$ inductive. The minimum active power in the stationary power regime is $P^{DG,min} = 30\text{ kW}$. Ramp-up and ramp-down rates are $P^{DG,RU} = 50\text{ kW/min}$ and $P^{DG,RD} = 50\text{ kW/min}$. The minimum number of cycles that the unit must be ON after startup is $N^{DG,on} = 6$ while it must be OFF $N^{DG,off} = 3$ cycles after shutdown. The fuel slope (ρ) and fuel intercept (σ) are set to 0.0015L/kWh and 0.215L/kWh respectively. The fuel cost (c^{fuel}) has been established in 1.2€/L.

Electricity costs ($c_t^{P,buy}$) are those established by the Iberian Electricity Market Operator (OMIE). Prices are made up of the hourly price resulting from the day-ahead energy market. In each scenario presented below, the hourly price for each period evaluated is reported. The excess energy fed into the distribution network is not paid. Thus, $c_t^{P,sell} = 0 \forall t$. The penalty for importing reactive power into the distribution network $c_t^{Q,buy}$ has been set at 0.041€/kVarh for the period between 8 a.m. to the end of the day and zero in the night period. Exporting reactive power is not penalized. Thus, $c_t^{Q,sell} = 0 \forall t$.

The EMS has been developed in Python using Gurobi as a solver. The

total number of variables employed by the solver for a 24-hour optimization horizon with a 15-minute time step is 7710. Of these, 6438 are continuous variables and 1272 are binary variables. The tests have been performed on a 11th Gen Intel(R) Core(TM) i5-11400 @ 2.60 GHz. The time required to solve the optimization problem is approximately 5s.

4. Results

This section presents the numerical results obtained after applying the EMS in the CATEPS Microgrid Living-Lab. To consider the variability that RESs and the building consumption could have, four representative weeks for each season of 2023 were selected to perform the experiments.

4.1. EMS operation in different seasons of the year

The optimal scheduling for the MG obtained with the proposed EMS is illustrated in Fig. 7. The figure shows the results in four different weeks, one for each season of the year: summer, autumn, winter and spring.

The left vertical axis represents active power in per-unit. Positive values indicate power injected at the MG nodes. Four power variables are represented: the power exchanged with the grid (i.e. power at NO), the power generated by the DG, the total PV generation and the power exchanged by the BESS. In addition to these variables, the total consumption of the loads is represented by a blue line. The hourly energy price is depicted as a dashed gray line. In this sense, vertical axis on the right is dedicated for the energy price in €/kWh. The scenarios depicted in Fig. 7 are discussed in the following paragraphs.

In the summer scenario, the energy consumption is much lower (and almost constant). This is because the week corresponds to the month of August, when the staff is on vacation and the building has its lowest level of activity. The renewable energy production in the central hours of the day is higher than the load demand. In this case, the BESS charges to take advantage of this situation and discharges when there is no renewable production and prices are high.

In autumn and winter, the production of renewable energy exhibits a

Fig. 7. Active Power results of the proposed EMS in different seasons of the year. The power values on the right axis are in p.u. ($S_B = 30\text{kVA}$). The active power is aggregated by unit type. The energy price is represented on the left axis.

greater variability than it does in summer and spring. Furthermore, the load consumption is also higher, particularly during weekdays. It can be noticed how the DG only activates in the winter scenario when the electricity price is high. This fact will be further discussed later. Furthermore, it is worth noting that BESS works in conjunction with DG to supply the building's demand.

In the spring scenario, renewable energy production has less variability and load consumption is softer compared to autumn and winter. This is due to the mild temperatures in the city of Seville during that time of the year. In this scenario, the BESS, in conjunction with PV energy production, can satisfy the building's energy requirements during the central hours of the day, when prices are high.

As illustrated in the figure, wind power production is marginal in all four cases. There are two primary reasons for this: firstly, the installed power capacity is very small compared to the rest of the assets; and secondly, the wind conditions in the city of Seville are not usually very intense.

Furthermore, as previously stated, the DG only operates during weekday periods in winter. Justification for this can be found in the following: the size of the DG is much larger than the current load demand of the building. This is due to the fact that not all of the Polytechnic School's services have been transferred yet to this newly constructed building. As a result, the building's energy consumption has not yet reached the maximum expected level. Consequently, the power that could be provided by the DG is significantly below its rated capacity, leading to an unfavorable economic performance. To illustrate this, Fig. 8 depicts the cost of the energy produced by the DG as a function of the output power for different fuel prices. This relation is obtained using equation (30). The power axis is presented on a logarithmic scale, which makes it easier to see the energy price differences between working powers that deviate from the nominal power. As illustrated in the figure, for power operation below 100 kW, the economic efficiency of the DG generator is poor.

Finally, to demonstrate the advantage of using the proposed EMS, Table 3 shows a comparison of energy costs between using the EMS and not using it. Three different cases have been considered:

- EMS case. The MG is managed using the proposed EMS.
- No EMS. The RESs of the MG are generating but there is no energy management (i.e. dispatchable units are not managed).
- No DER. This case assumes that there is no DER in the building (i.e. all the energy is supplied from the distribution network).

In this sense, Table 3 shows the operating cost in euros for each of the scenarios. In addition, the percentage cost reduction achieved by using

Fig. 8. Cost of the energy produced by the DG as function of the output power considering different fuel prices.

Table 3

Energy cost comparison between using the EMS, not using it and not having DER installed in the building.

Scenario	Energy cost (€)			EMS Cost reduction (%)	
	EMS	No EMS	No DERs	No EMS	No DER
Summer	340.72	435.93	782.09	21.84	56.43
Autumn	883.73	944.44	1146.77	6.43	22.94
Winter	1495.28	1585.52	1748.74	5.69	14.94
Spring	395.21	464.08	737.93	14.84	46.44

EMS compared to the “No EMS” and “No DER” cases are shown. As can be seen, the highest cost reduction is obtained in summer and spring, with a cost reduction of 21.84 % and a 14.84 % respectively compared to the “No EMS” case. However, in autumn and winter, the cost reduction is 6.43 % and 5.51 % respectively compared to the “No EMS” case. The difference in the cost reduction can be explained by the fact that in summer and spring the load consumption is lower and the BESS has room to shift the energy absorbed from the distribution network from periods of high prices to periods of low prices. Furthermore, in summer and spring, the PV production has less variability and the BESS can work better in conjunction with it, especially during the central hours of the day (when PV production is at its maximum). In summer, the BESS is charging in the central hours of the day to take advantage of the energy surplus. However, in spring, the BESS is discharged to avoid buying energy during high-price periods.

4.2. Voltage and reactive power management

One of the advantages of the proposed EMS is its ability to manage not only economic aspects but also technical constraints, such as voltage and reactive power management. This subsection presents the results regarding voltages at the nodes of the MG and reactive power management at it.

Fig. 9 shows the voltage magnitude trend over the four weeks considered in the previous subsection. For each scenario, two plots are presented, one at the top of the subfigure to illustrate the voltages at nodes with PV generation (N8 to N11) and one at the bottom of the subfigure for the remaining nodes. The objective of this split is to provide a more comprehensive representation, given the significant scale differences between the voltages at the PV nodes and compared to those in the rest of the network.

As can be observed, the nodes where PV generation is present (N8 to N11) exhibit greater voltage deviation. This is due to the fact that these nodes are the most distant within the MG (see Fig. 5). Furthermore, the branches feeding them exhibit the smallest cross-sectional area and, therefore, the highest resistance within the MG, as evidenced in Table 2. Moreover, among these nodes, those exhibiting the greatest voltage deviation (N10 and N11) are those connected to the rest of the MG by the branches with the smallest cross-section. Although the voltage at these nodes is the highest recorded in the MG, it is always below 2 %, which is a value well within the bounds and does not warrant concern. The remaining nodes (N0 to N7) exhibit a smoother voltage profile. Among these nodes, it is noteworthy the voltage fluctuations in N3, which is devoted to the BESS.

In Fig. 10, the reactive power balance is shown. As well as in the rest of the figures, positive values indicate inductive power injected into the node. It is important to note that the only assets of the MG capable of modulating reactive power are the PV inverters and the WT inverter. The DG operates at a fixed power factor of 0.8 inductive. The loads at the building are predominantly inductive. Thus, the variables represented in Fig. 10, are the reactive power imported from the distribution network, the total reactive power managed by the PV and WT inverters and the reactive power by the DG. The total reactive power required by the loads is overlaid in the figure with a blue line. As illustrated in the figure, the MG does not inject reactive power into the distribution network. In the

Fig. 9. Voltage trend for all the nodes in the microgrid over the four scenarios considered in the paper. The voltage trends are divided into two subplots for each scenario: one for the PV nodes at the top (N8 to N11) and other at the bottom for the rest of the nodes.

Fig. 10. Reactive power results of the proposed EMS in different seasons of the year. The power values on the right axis are in p.u. ($S_B = 30\text{kVA}$). The reactive power is aggregated by unit type.

central hours of the day, the PV inverters are injecting reactive power, which serves to compensate for the load demand and avoid having to import from the distribution network. It is worthy of note that the DG is compensating for the reactive power demanded by the loads when operating in a winter scenario. An examination of the same period of the winter scenario in Fig. 7 reveals that the DG is not providing all the active power required by the loads. Instead, the DG is operating in

conjunction with the BESS. Thus, in this case, the DG is fulfilling a dual role: firstly, it is contributing to the reduction of reactive demand to avoid penalties, and secondly, it is providing the required active power demanded by the loads in conjunction with the BESS.

Fig. 11 presents a graphical illustration of the reactive power management capabilities of the inverters. The figure depicts the active, reactive, and apparent power variables, along with the power factor, for

Fig. 11. Assessment of the reactive power management of one of the PV inverters. The figure shows the active, reactive, and apparent power, as well as the power factor at which the inverter is operating.

one of the PV inverters. The power factor sign is expressed in accordance with the IEEE convention. It is important to recall that PV inverters have a maximum power rating of 15kVA and that the minimum power factor at which they can operate is 0.85 (both inductive and capacitive). As can be seen in Fig. 11, the inverters are providing reactive power to the MG,

thus, they are operating with an inductive power factor with respect to the load. At the beginning and end of the day, when the PV production is significantly below the maximum active power rating, the inverter operates at a power factor of 0.85 inductive, with the objective of maximizing the reactive power injected into the MG. However, at the

Fig. 12. Voltage magnitude and phase angle trend at various nodes of the MG. The figure shows the results obtained with the proposed linear power flow equations and with the complete non-linear equations.

central hours of the day, when the active power production is higher, the inverter reduces the reactive power production to comply with its apparent power capability rating. This serves to validate the power electronics model presented in Subsection 2.1.

4.3. Validation of linearized power flow equations

This subsection presents a comparison between the results given by the proposed linearized power flow equations for modeling the MG network, as presented in subsection 2.6, and those obtained with a complete non-linear model. To conduct this comparison, the GridCal package was used [44]. GridCal is a power flow solver with a graphical interface and a Python API. In this case, the Python API was employed to model the MG. The active and reactive power scheduling provided by the EMS were used as inputs for the power flow solver. With these parameters, the classical Newton-Raphson iterative method [45] was used in the power flow solver to obtain the voltages and phase angles at all the nodes of the network.

Fig. 12 presents the voltage magnitude and phase angle at various nodes of the MG. Specifically, at nodes N10, N3 and N2 which are one of the PV nodes, the BESS node and the central node of the MG, respectively (see Fig. 5). The subplots on the left illustrate the voltage magnitude, while those on the right illustrate the phase angle. The results depicted in the figure correspond to the autumn scenario, in which there is a good level of variability in the variables. The values obtained with the proposed EMS are depicted in solid red color while the values obtained with the non-linear power flow solver are shown with a dashed blue line. As can be observed, there is no perceptible difference.

To further study the possible discrepancies, the Mean Absolute Error (MAE) between the results obtained with the proposed approach and those obtained using the complete non-linear power flow equations has been obtained. The Mean Absolute Error (MAE) is defined as equation (42):

$$MAE = \frac{\sum_{i=0}^{n_{samples}-1} |y_i - \hat{y}_i|}{n_{samples}} \quad (42)$$

where y_i is the value expected for the variable, \hat{y}_i the value obtained in the experiment and $n_{samples}$ the number of samples in the timeseries. Fig. 13 shows a heatmap displaying the MAE values for voltage magnitude and phase angle obtained for the four scenarios under

consideration and for all the nodes in the MG. The reported values demonstrate minimal discrepancy between the values obtained with the proposed approach and those obtained with the complete non-linear equations. The nodes with the highest difference are N8 to N11, which are also the ones that exhibit the most pronounced voltage deviation (see Fig. 9). However, the error in these nodes is insignificant. As a conclusion, the proposed power flow linearization obtains results that are comparable to those that could be obtained using the complete equations and, therefore, with other types of convex quadratic formulations.

4.4. Dispatchable units ON/OFF limitations: Evaluation on the BESS model

The proposed EMS implements constraints to manage the ON/OFF cycles of dispatchable units (i.e., BESS and DG). In this subsection, the effect of these constraints in the BESS model is evaluated.

First, to demonstrate the model's ability to adapt to the limitations of ON/OFF cycles, Fig. 14 presents the results for a specific winter day, considering three different configurations for the minimum ON/OFF cycles of the BESS. The figure is made up of three subfigures, each of which varies the ON/OFF parameters. In each subfigure, the active power balance (in a manner analogous to that depicted in Fig. 7) is presented, as well as the state of the binary variables indicating the charging and discharging status of the BESS. The number of ON cycles in both charge and discharge modes has been considered equal. Similarly, for OFF cycles, they have been considered equal for charge and discharge. As can be seen, the BESS operates in accordance with the established minimum requirements in the three scenarios.

Within the three cases, some interesting behaviors can be highlighted. For example, in the upper subfigure, it can be observed that there are two instances in a discharging period when the device shut-downs for just one cycle and subsequently resumes operation (as $N^{BESS,off,X}$ is equal to 1). However, by modifying $N^{BESS,off,X} = 2$ in the case depicted in the central subfigure, the BESS groups the two discharge periods into a single period, thereby reducing the number of on/off switching cycles and the resulting stress on the battery.

Another noteworthy phenomenon can be observed during the central hours of the day, when the battery is discharging. In the upper subfigure (with $N^{BESS,on,X} = 3$), the battery discharges primarily at the two price

MAE: Voltage					MAE: Phase Angle				
	Summer	Autumn	Winter	Spring		Summer	Autumn	Winter	Spring
N0	0.0e+00	0.0e+00	0.0e+00	0.0e+00	N0	0.0e+00	0.0e+00	0.0e+00	0.0e+00
N1	1.7e-06	2.5e-07	4.7e-07	1.4e-06	N1	4.2e-06	6.1e-07	8.2e-07	3.5e-06
N2	2.2e-06	3.2e-07	5.7e-07	1.8e-06	N2	5.4e-06	7.8e-07	1.1e-06	4.5e-06
N3	2.2e-06	3.6e-07	7.5e-07	1.9e-06	N3	5.4e-06	7.9e-07	1.1e-06	4.5e-06
N4	4.4e-06	6.4e-07	1.0e-06	3.7e-06	N4	6.0e-06	8.7e-07	1.2e-06	5.0e-06
N5	3.2e-06	4.7e-07	7.7e-07	2.7e-06	N5	6.3e-06	9.0e-07	1.2e-06	5.2e-06
N6	9.1e-06	1.6e-06	2.4e-06	7.6e-06	N6	7.4e-06	1.2e-06	1.5e-06	6.2e-06
N7	5.3e-06	7.7e-07	1.2e-06	4.4e-06	N7	7.5e-06	1.1e-06	1.4e-06	6.2e-06
N8	3.2e-05	5.3e-06	5.5e-06	2.6e-05	N8	8.2e-06	1.8e-06	1.7e-06	7.1e-06
N9	5.1e-05	7.4e-06	8.2e-06	4.1e-05	N9	1.7e-05	2.9e-06	3.2e-06	1.5e-05
N10	8.8e-05	1.3e-05	1.4e-05	7.0e-05	N10	3.2e-05	5.1e-06	5.4e-06	2.7e-05
N11	8.3e-05	1.2e-05	1.3e-05	6.7e-05	N11	3.0e-05	5.0e-06	5.4e-06	2.7e-05

Fig. 13. Mean Absolute Error for the voltage magnitude and phase angle between the results obtained with the proposed linearized power flow equations and with the complete non-linear ones.

Fig. 14. EMS results for three different ON/OFF configurations for the BESS unit. Each scenario is illustrated with two subfigures. In each scenario, the subfigure at the top depicts the active power variables (on the left axis) and the electricity price (on the right axis), while the bottom subfigure depicts the state of the binary variables (0 or 1), indicating the charging and discharging status of the BESS.

peaks that appear. By increasing the minimum number of ON cycles in the cases at the middle and at the bottom (with $N^{BESS,on,X} = 6$ and $N^{BESS,on,X} = 12$ respectively), it can be observed that in order to comply with the minimums imposed, the BESS discharges at a high power at the two peak prices while maintaining a minimum power (established by equation (20)) between them. This similar behavior is observed at the beginning and the end of the day, when the BESS is charging.

To assess the impact of the $N^{BESS,on,X}$ and $N^{BESS,off,X}$ parameters on the overall cost of the MG operation, Table 4 reports the weekly energy price for each of the four weekly scenarios considered in the paper. It should be noted that the minimum ON/OFF cycles for charging and discharging are considered equal. In addition to the weekly price, Table 4 also shows the total energy exchanged by the BESS and the total number of startups (both in charging and discharging) in the week under consideration. As evidenced by the results, the minimum limitation of the ON/OFF cycle has no discernible impact on the economic cost. Similarly, no significant differences are observed in the total energy exchanged by the BESS. However, as the minimum ON/OFF cycle limit increases, the number of

startups decreases, reducing the stress on the BESS.

As a conclusion, the restrictions on minimum ON/OFF cycles for dispatchable units are useful for establishing technical constraints, without significantly impacting the overall operating costs of the MG.

4.5. Power and SoC relationship in the BESS model

A distinctive feature of the proposed BESS model is its capacity to relate the state of charge (SoC) and the maximum power it can deliver. Specifically, the BESS model presented in subsection 2.4 limits the maximum power that the battery can inject or absorb from the grid as a function of its SoC and mode of operation (charging or discharging). A summary of the constraints to define the operational region of the BESS was depicted in Fig. 2. This particular feature is not commonly observed in the existing literature.

To assess the effectiveness of the constraints defined for the BESS, Fig. 15 depicts the active power exchanged by the battery as function of the SoC for each of the scenarios presented in the paper. The power is normalized by the maximum power of the BESS power electronics (30 kW). The figure represents the weekly results of the four scenarios presented in the paper. To provide context for the constraints imposed on the BESS operation, the dashed gray lines represent the operating limits in a manner analogous to that depicted in Fig. 2 of in subsection 2.4. For the purposes of the following discussion, the gray dotted line can be ignored.

As illustrated in Fig. 15, all points are within the area of operation. That is to say, the points lie between the lower and upper limits established for the SoC, above the minimum power required for operation and considering the power limits for discharging and charging. An interesting behavior can be observed in the discharge phase (positive power values): the power does not reach the upper limit when the state of charge (SoC) falls below 0.2 (gray dashed line). At first glance, it may appear that there is an issue with the definition of the constraint (22). However, this behavior is a consequence of the implicit power constraint that arises from the energy remaining in the battery, considering the minimum battery SoC imposed. In other words, if the remaining energy

Table 4

Weekly EMS operational cost of the EMS, the total energy exchanged by the BESS, and the number of startups of the BESS (either to charge or discharge), under different numbers of minimum ON/OFF cycles in different scenarios.

Scenario	ON	OFF	Cost (€)	Total energy exchanged by the BESS (kWh)	Number of startups
Summer	3	1	340.72	1092.53	28
	6	2	340.93	1100.83	20
	12	4	341.03	1074.53	16
Autumn	3	1	883.73	1518.10	30
	6	2	883.78	1518.34	29
	12	4	883.84	1518.47	22
Winter	3	1	1495.28	1657.17	37
	6	2	1495.42	1657.17	32
	12	4	1495.50	1656.57	24
Spring	3	1	395.21	1464.23	32
	6	2	395.39	1399.89	24
	12	4	395.78	1407.72	21

Fig. 15. Active power exchanged by the BESS as function of the SoC. The gray lines represent the operational limits defined in the BESS model.

in the battery is close to the minimum level ($SoC_i^{BESS,min}$), the maximum power that could provide the BESS would be limited by the remaining energy stored, the time interval Δt and the efficiency of the power electronics. For the discharging case, this implicit constraint can be expressed by the inequality (43). The function of the gray dotted line in Fig. 15 can now be elucidated: it corresponds to this implicit constraint.

In a similar way, inequality (44) represents the implicit constraint for the charging case. In contrast to the discharge case, this constraint has a minimal effect in the case shown in Fig. 15 (gray dotted line in the discharge area). This is because the maximum allowed SoC is closer to 100 % than the minimum allowed SoC is from 0 %.

$$P_{i,t}^{BESS} \leq \frac{\eta_i^{dis} (SoC_{i,t}^{BESS} - SoC_i^{BESS,min}) W_i^{BESS,cap}}{\Delta t} \quad (43)$$

$$P_{i,t}^{BESS} \geq \frac{(SoC_{i,t}^{BESS} - SoC_i^{BESS,max}) W_i^{BESS,cap}}{\eta_i^{ch} \Delta t} \quad (44)$$

As a conclusion for this subsection, the correct operation of the constraints that have been included into the EMS to link the state of charge (SoC) to the maximum power that can be exchanged by the BESS has been validated. However, depending on the SoC limits, constraints (43)-(44) may be more restrictive.

5. Conclusions

The increasing presence of DERs requires the implementation of an effective management strategy. MGs offer an effective solution for the integration of RESs, BESS units, CCHP units, DG units, etc. in the distribution network.

This paper contributes with a comprehensive EMS for the optimal operation of generic grid-tied MGs, with the objective of reducing the operational costs. The proposed EMS considers several key aspects, including active and reactive power management, the application of power flow equations, the use of specific models for power electronics units and dispatchable units, and the integration of detailed device models for BESSs and DGs. In order to reduce the computational

requirements while ensuring the existence of an optimal solution that represents the global minimum, the EMS is formulated as a MILP optimization problem. Consequently, all the constraints have been linearized.

The main functionalities of the proposed EMS have been assessed in a use case that involves a representative facility: the CATEPS Microgrid Living-Lab. The EMS operation of the MG was evaluated in different seasons which showed a significant cost reduction in the MG operation when using the proposed EMS, especially in the summer (21.84 %) and spring (14.84 %) scenarios. Furthermore, the operation of the DG in the proposed scenarios was examined. The findings indicated that, given the size of the DG and the current load of the building in question, its operation becomes economically viable only when electricity prices reach elevated levels.

A detailed focus was given to reactive power and voltage management, showing the capacity of RES to compensate for reactive power, ensuring the operational limits of the inverters. Furthermore, to validate the linearization of the power flow equations, a comparison was conducted between the proposed power flow equations and the complete non-linear ones. In this sense, the voltage results (magnitude and angle) obtained by the proposed EMS were then contrasted with those yielded by a power flow solver employing the complete non-linear equations. The MAE metric demonstrated minimal discrepancies between the linear and non-linear equations: $8.8e-5$ p.u. and $3.2e-5$ rad for voltage magnitude and phase angle respectively; thereby proving the effectiveness of the proposed approach.

The dispatchable units ON/OFF model constraints were assessed using the BESS as a case study, which demonstrated the ability of the proposed model to modulate the startup and shutdown periods of the device. The results indicated that the ON/OFF parameters had an imperceptible impact on the operating costs and on the total energy exchanged by the BESS. This finding suggests that the technical limitations of the device can be addressed while maintaining a minimal impact on the operational cost. For instance, the total number of startups in a typical winter week was reduced from 37 to 24 while the difference in operational costs just increased by 0.22€, with the total energy exchanged by the BESS remaining almost constant in both scenarios (from 1657.17kWh to 1656.57kWh). Furthermore, the dependence

between the maximum charging and discharging power on the SoC was also evaluated. The results validated the linear model introduced to implement this relationship. Moreover, the results showed that the inherent relationship between the available energy in the BESS and the maximum power may be more restrictive, depending on the maximum and minimum SoC and on the delta time adopted in the optimization process.

Future research will address the impact of the forecast accuracy due to the inherent stochasticity of RESs. This will involve exploring potential solutions to mitigate this aspect using probabilistic forecasting techniques and a rolling horizon optimization approach, with the aim of dynamically updating the EMS execution. The proposed EMS is intended for a tertiary control of grid-connected MGs, future research will also address the inclusion of secondary and primary control (p-f and v-q control) to support the operation of the CATEPS MG in islanded mode as well as the integration of the proposed EMS into the SCADA system.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Sebastián García: Writing – original draft, Software, Methodology,

Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Stefano Bracco:** Writing – original draft, Validation, Investigation. **Antonio Parejo:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Validation. **Matteo Fresia:** Writing – original draft, Validation, Investigation. **Juan Ignacio Guerrero:** Writing – review & editing, Resources, Project administration, Data curation. **Carlos León:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgements

The publication is part of the project TED2021-129702B-I00, funded by MICIU/AEI/10.13039/501100011033 and the European Union “NextGenerationEU”/PRTR.

Appendix A. . MILP formulation for obtaining absolute values

Let be x a continuous variable in the range $[-C, C]$ with C being a constant value. The absolute value of x can be obtained imposing the following set of constraints:

$$x \leq aM \quad (45)$$

$$x \geq (a-1)M \quad (46)$$

$$x - y \leq (1-a)M \quad (47)$$

$$x - y \geq (a-1)M \quad (48)$$

$$x + y \leq aM \quad (49)$$

$$x + y \geq aM \quad (50)$$

where a is a binary variable, M a big positive number ($M \geq 2C$) and y a positive continuous variable. Constraints (45) and (46) are used to set $a = 1$ if x is positive and $a = 0$ if negative. Constraints (47) and (48) are used to impose $y = x$ when x is positive while constraints (49) and (50) are used to impose $y = -x$ when x is negative. Therefore, imposing constraints (45)-(50) is the same that $y = |x|$.

Appendix B. . MILP formulation to linearize the product of a binary and a continuous variable

Let x be a continuous variable $x \in [-C, C]$ with C being a constant value. Let be a a binary variable. The non-linear product of x and a can be linearized replacing it by a continuous auxiliary variable $g \triangleq ax$ if the following set of constraints are imposed:

$$g \geq -Ma \quad (51)$$

$$g \leq Ma \quad (52)$$

$$g \leq x + M(1-a) \quad (53)$$

$$g \geq x - M(1-a) \quad (54)$$

where M is a big positive number ($M \geq C$). Constraints (51) and (52) sets $g = 0$ if $a = 0$ while (53) and (54) imposes $g = x$ if $a = 1$.

Data availability

The data that has been used is confidential.

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